

Should we ban one-to-one tablets? Analyzing Discursive Manifestations of Contradictions in Educational Technology Integration in Secondary Education

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Abstract: *The integration of digital technology in secondary education presents significant policy challenges for school leaders. While technology has been integrated in the last decade with the promise of supporting active learning pedagogies, it has produced tensions in the teaching-learning activity system, including increased distractions, potential cognitive impacts, and limitations for students with learning difficulties. This study examines the educational impact of technologies through an ecological observational study in two secondary schools with different technology integration policies. The study identifies contradictions in technology integration and their implications for policy recommendations for school leaders.*

Keywords: *Secondary Education, Contradictions, Educational Technology, Tablets*

Introduction

The widespread integration of technology in educational settings, driven by goals of digital literacy and active learning pedagogies (Sailer et al. 2024), has also raised concerns about its limitations and unintended consequences, such as significant distractions. Personal technology can be a substantial source of distraction (Flanigan & Babchuk, 2022). The introduction of one-to-one devices, through devices provided by the school or students' own devices, has raised tension in the teaching and learning activities in secondary education. This study evaluates the impacts of technology use through the lens of Cultural Historical Activity Theory (CHAT), aiming to identify the contradictions within the teaching-learning activity system in secondary education. In Cultural-Historical Activity Theory (CHAT), contradictions are central to understanding the dynamics of an activity system, serving as the driving force for change and development (Engeström & Sannino, 2011; Engeström et al., 2024; Isaac et al., 2022; Romero & Barma, 2022). Contradictions are historically embedded structural tensions within an activity system or between different activity systems. These underlying contradictions manifest as observable symptoms, which can include various forms of tensions in relation to the integration of technology in secondary education.

Method

This study employed a qualitative research design grounded in the principles of third-generation CHAT (Engeström, 2001). The research objective was to analyse the teaching and learning activity mediated by technological tools in secondary school classrooms, focusing on the potential contradictions that arise from their integration. Participants were involved from two secondary schools in Catalonia, both with a long-standing tradition since 1964. In School 1, teachers must request access to a computer lab or mobile devices for specific technology-dependent activities, as the school does not operate a one-to-one device programme. In contrast, School 2 implements a one-to-one tablet policy, providing each student with an iPad for use both inside and outside the school environment.

A two-phase methodology was carried out: an initial stage of intensive classroom observation and a second step involving a focus group. An observational coding grid, based on CHAT-based studies, was developed to capture and analyse interactions, integrating student actions related to direct engagement, collaborative, and individual learning. The coding schema was structured into three main dimensions: Social (XSK), Content (XCK), and Resources (XRK). The observations were naturalistic and non-interventionist, reported through the coding schema in 10-minute intervals. After the observational study, we organised focus groups, held in each school, including three learners, three teachers, two family members, and two teaching staff members. The recorded discussions were transcribed and analysed through the coding schema and by identifying discursive manifestations of contradictions (Engeström & Sannino, 2011).

Results

The study identified diverse discursive manifestations of contradictions arising from technology integration in educational settings. A significant tension emerged regarding technology as a learning tool versus a source of distraction. While participants acknowledged technology's value for research and fostering engagement, particularly in subjects like mathematics, its unstructured access frequently led to disengagement and distraction. This was evident in observations where students, despite having tools meant for learning, often diverted their attention to non-academic applications. Another manifestation of contradictions was observed around the controlled versus uncontrolled use of technology. Schools grappled with maintaining control over digital environments; even with strict device policies, constant supervision was required, and past incidents of misuse contributed to heightened teacher difficulties regarding the misuse of technology provided by the school. This challenge was particularly pronounced in School 2, which adopted a 1:1 tablet policy, leading to increased efforts to manage student digital behaviour. In School 2, the students' reliance on digital devices posed a significant issue due to the lack of readily available alternative non-digital learning tools. Despite the availability of tablets in School 2, their use was significantly limited by restrictive policies, leading to a tension between the devices' capabilities and their actual application in learning. A second tension emerged between the school's digital resources and the learning activity itself. Specifically, School 1's limited availability of digital devices necessitated advance planning for any technology-based activities. This constraint led to a more intentional and, as observed, positive use of technology, as its integration was always a deliberate choice. From a school-family perspective, the study revealed an underlying tension between family expectations and the school's utilisation of technology. Parents held divergent views; some advocated for stringent regulations on screen time and digital device use, while others strongly believed digital tools were fundamental for providing a "modern education". This disparity in parental perspectives created uncertainty for schools in establishing consistent and effective technology integration policies that could bridge the home-school divide.

Discussion

These results highlight the necessity of structuring technology regulation at the school level. While personal devices such as the tablets in School 2 can facilitate information access, they also introduce cognitive overload and distractions, requiring further regulation from teachers, families and the learners themselves. When school- or teacher-level regulation is not provided, learners must self-regulate, which is challenging for learners given their developmental stage. Without a well-defined digital policy at the school leadership level, teachers, families and learners struggle to regulate technology in secondary education. Parents' divergent perspectives on technology use further contribute to these tensions, with some equating technology with innovation and others concerned about screen time and distraction. For successful technology integration, policy must be created collaboratively with all stakeholders, including teachers, school staff, leadership, families and learners, to define the school policy on technology-enhanced learning and ensure alignment of family-school digital practices.

References

Engeström, Y., & Sannino, A. (2011). Discursive manifestations of contradictions in organizational change efforts: A methodological framework. *Journal of organizational change management*, 24(3), 368-387.

- Engeström, Y., Rantavuori, P., Ruutu, P., & Tapola-Haapala, M. (2024). The hybridisation of adolescents' worlds as a source of developmental tensions: a study of discursive manifestations of contradictions. *Educational Review*, 76(2), 321-342.
- Flanigan, A. E., & Babchuk, W. A. (2022). Digital distraction in the classroom: exploring instructor perceptions and reactions. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 27(3), 352-370.
- Isaac, G., Romero, M., & Barma, S. (2022). Understanding co-creativity in real-world problem solving in project-based learning in higher education. *Revue internationale du CRIRES*, 6(3), 86-99.
- Romero, M., & Barma, S. (2022). Analysing an interactive problem-solving task through the lens of double stimulation. *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology*, 48(1).
- Sailer, M., Maier, R., Berger, S., Kastorff, T., & Stegmann, K. (2024). Learning activities in technology-enhanced learning: A systematic review of meta-analyses and second-order meta-analysis in higher education. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 112, 102446.